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SEXUAL VIOLENCE IN NIGERIA: IMPEDIMENTS TO PROSECUTION OF RAPE CASES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Rape, simply put, is a sexual affair which is being done with force or without consent of both parties. However, rape goes beyond the simple understanding of layman. Its different faces and deepening effects are not exhaustively explored, and much is left untapped to contend with the menace. Therefore, the broad objective of this study is to critically examine the impediment of the prosecution of rape cases in Nigeria. The research methodology was doctrinal approach, using expository and appraisal research design. The sources of data collection were various legal literatures, both from the physical library and the e-library. It was observed that, there is a need to overhaul the entire gamut of the law of rape in Nigeria. Therefore, it was recommended among others that Nigerian legislators and the judiciary should adopt sound principles of activism instead of playing according to letters of statute alone.

Keywords: Rape, carnal knowledge, Victim, penetration, organs.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Rape is the most serious kind of assault¹; it is also referred to as unlawful carnal knowledge. It has been defined as a crime of aggression, power, and control in which one person forces, coerces, or manipulates another person to have sexual intercourse without their consent.² The offence of rape has been identified as one of the most under-reported crimes³ and one of the commonest crimes of personal violence. According to the women at Risk international Foundation, Africa has the highest prevalence rate of child sexual abuse, which is around 34.4%.⁴ Findings from a national survey carried out in 2014 on violence against children in Nigeria confirmed that one in four females reported experiencing sexual violence in children, with approximately 70% reporting more than one incident of sexual violence. In the same study, it was found that 24.8% of females between ages eighteen (18) to twenty-four (24) years experienced sexual abuse before age eighteen (18) of which 5.0% sought help, with only 3.5% receiving any services.⁵

In some African societies, including Nigeria, the victims of rape do not only suffer the emotional trauma from the experience, they also suffer the shame of identification associated with it in those societies. The societies blame them for being the cause of their ordeals; they are stigmatized and treated as immoral and unclean. These contribute largely to the refusal of most victims to report cases of rape, and invariably the continued perpetration of the criminal act.

However, in Nigeria, the need to bring the perpetrators to justice has been emphasized over the years, and laws have been and are being enacted to ensure that the offence is defined and punishment prescribed for it. Initially, the existing laws on the offence were the Criminal Code⁶ and the penal Code⁷ governing the southern and northern parts of Nigeria respectively, which were also adopted as laws in the 36 states and the Federal Capital

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¹ Oluyemis Bamgbose and Sonia Akinbiyi, *Criminal Law in Nigeria* (Ibadan: Evans Brothers Nigeria Publisher, 2015)175

² <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2017/09/lets-talk-rape/Accessed> 10th April 2023.

³ CMV Clarkson and HMKeating, *Criminal Law: Texts and Materials* (London: Sweet and Maxwell Publishers 1984)469.

⁴ <http://warifng.org/rape-stats-in-nigeria/>>Accessed 10th April 2023.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ CAP C38.L FN 2004.

⁷ CAP P3, Vol.13, LFN 2004.

Territory. Both laws and their municipal representations define the offence and stipulate the punishments to be meted on the offenders. However, as the perpetrators of rape became more apparent so, it became necessary to enact more laws to bring perpetrators to book and make provision for the compensation and protection of the victims of this heinous crime. It is in a bid to satisfy this need that more Federal and state laws such as Administration of Criminal Justices Act, 2015; Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act, 2015; Violence Against Women Law and so on, on the crime of rape enacted in Nigeria.

2.0 DEFINITION AND INGREDIENTS OF THE OFFENCE

2.1 DEFINITION OF RAPE

Section 357 of the Criminal Code and section 282 of the Penal Code define the offence of rape. According to Section 357 of the Criminal Code⁸:

Any person who has unlawful carnal knowledge of a woman or girl, without her consent, or with her consent, if the consent is obtained by force or by means of threats or intimidation of any kind, or fear of harm, or by means of false and fraudulent representations as to the nature of the act, or, in the case of married women, by impersonating her husband, is guilty of an offence which is called rape.

In section 282 of the Penal Code⁹ rape is defined as follows:

A man is said to commit rape which save in the case referred to in subsection (2) has sexual intercourse with a woman in any of the following circumstances:

- a. against her will;
- b. without her consent;
- c. With her consent, when her consent has been obtained by putting her in fear of death or of hurt;
- d. With her consent, when the man knows that her consent is given because she believes that he is another man whom she is or believes herself to be lawfully married;

⁸ CAP C38, LFN2004.

⁹ CAP P3, Vol.13, LFN204.

- e. With or without her consent¹⁰, when she is under fourteen years of age or of unsound mind.

The definitions above show that the offence of rape is committed when a person engages in sexual intercourse with a woman or girl without her consent, or with her consent where such consent is obtained by force or fraud.

2.2 INGREDIENTS OF THE OFFENCE UNDER THE CRIMINAL CODE ACT IN NIGERIA

From the above cited provisions, the following are the ingredients necessary to prove rape:

- i. Sexual Intercourse (Carnal Knowledge)

The physical element of the offence of rape which must be proved is that a person had unlawful carnal knowledge or sexual intercourse with a woman. Carnal knowledge is complete upon penetration. According to the law, penetration is when the male organ reaches the labia minora outside the vagina of the woman¹¹. In other words, rape is an offence under the criminal law that can only be committed by a male as an offender, and on a woman as a victim¹². Penetration must be through the vagina and not through the anus¹³. It is not necessary to prove that the hymen was ruptured or that there was an emission of semen¹⁴, the slightest penetration of the vagina with the penis would suffice¹⁵. This distinguishes the present position of the law in Nigeria under the Criminal Code Act from the English Law where penetration could be vaginal or anal.

In the Ugandan case of *Mukasa Evensto v. Uganda*¹⁶, the Ugandan Court of Appeal held that it is trite law that penetration however slight will suffice, the vagina need not be fully penetrated and proof of rupture of hymen is not necessary. The Court pointed out that although the victim's hymen was not broken, there was penetration. Again, in *Muzeeyimana Phillip v. Uganda*¹⁷, the Ugandan Court of Appeal held that, it is a trite law that the slightest penetration is sufficient. In that case, sexual intercourse was proved by

¹⁰ See *Ogunbayo v state* (2007) 8NWLR (pt1045)157;

¹¹ *R. v Kufi* (1960) WRNLR 1.

¹² *Ahmed v. Nigerian Army* (2011) 1 NWLR (Pt. 1227) 89 CA; *Ogunbayo v. State* (2007) 8 NWLR (Pt. 1035) 157; *Iko v. State* (2001) 14 NWLR (Pt. 732) 221; *Jegade v. State* (2001) 14 NWLR (Pt. 733) 264.

¹³ *Iko v. State* (2001) 14 NWLR (Pt. 732) 221.

¹⁴ *R v. Marsden* (1891) 2 Q. B. 14, *R. v. Hughes* (1841) 9 C & P 752.

¹⁵ *C.M.V. Clarkson and H.M. Keating* (n 3); *People (Att.-Gen.) v. Dermody* (1956) I.R. at 32; *Criminal Code* (n 5).

¹⁶ C/A 53/99.

¹⁷ C/A no. 85/1999.

the inflammation of the *versibule*. Evidence was led to the effect that such inflammation usually follows an act of sexual intercourse.

Moreover, it has been established that ejaculation is not one of the requirements of the offence of rape¹⁸. Thus, without penetration, the offence is complete upon penetration, the other acts of sexual intercourse which may follow are parts of the offence itself and it has been held that aid given after penetration makes the aider a party to the offence¹⁹.

Furthermore, it must be shown that the sexual intercourse was unlawful. Unlawful carnal knowledge has always been taken to refer to intercourse outside the bonds of marriage; this is because a woman is deemed to consent to the act of sexual intercourse by the marriage ceremony²⁰. This is also shown in Section 6 of the Criminal Code that provides that “When the term ‘carnal knowledge’ or the term ‘carnal connection’ is used in defining an offence, it is implied that the offence, so far as regards that element of it, is complete upon penetration. ‘Unlawful carnal knowledge’ means carnal connection which takes place otherwise than between husband and wife”. Therefore, in Nigeria, a husband cannot be found guilty of rape, even where the wife does not consent. However, this is a privilege or immunity for the husband. Any sexual intercourse by the husband with the wife without her consent would not amount to rape²¹. Furthermore, a husband can be guilty of aiding and abetting to commit rape by virtue of Section 7(b) of the Criminal Code²² for husband cannot transfer his implied consent to sexual intercourse with his wife to another person²³.

ii. Lack of Consent

This element is very crucial as it is the lack of consent that transforms normal sexual intercourse into rape. The prosecution has to prove that the accused had carnal knowledge of a woman or a girl, despite her age, without her consent²⁴. It has been held that it is no excuse that the complainant is a common prostitute, that she had consented to intercourse with the accused on other occasions or that she is the accused person’s concubine.

¹⁸ Halsbury Laws of England, (Vol. 10, 3rd edn) (Butterworth, 1954) para, 1438 at 746.

¹⁹ R v. Mayberry (1973) Q.R. 211 (Skerman J. dissenting).

²⁰ Section 6 of the Criminal Code.

²¹ Oluyemisi Bamgbose and Sonia Akinbiyi (n 1) 184.

²² DPP v Morgan (1975) 2 AER 347; R v. Waite (1892) 2 Q B 6.

²³ R v. Morgan (n 22); R v. Shivpuri 1987 AC 1; R v. Seymour 1983 2 AC 443.

²⁴ n 11.

According to the law, consent obtained by force or by means of threats or intimidation or fear of harm is not consent. Consent given because of exhaustion after persistent struggle and resistance would appear to be no consent and to have carnal knowledge of a sleeping woman, or by personating her husband is rape. Also, submission by a person of weak intellect, or a person who is too young to understand the nature of the act done is not consent²⁵.

Furthermore, it is important in proving the offence of rape, to show that the accused intended to have sexual intercourse with the victim without her consent.

3.0 THE NIGERIAN CRIMINAL CODE ACT²⁶

The criminal Code Act is the federal law regulating criminal conducts in southern Nigeria. The act first became law in Nigeria in 1916, initially standing as the only federal Act on the subject, and being applicable to the whole of the federation. The Code is contained in the Schedule to the Act establishing the Criminal Law in Nigeria. The Code defines rape and stipulates the punishment to be meted out on offenders. The provision and requirements have been partially discussed above.

In addition to the discussion above, the Act provides for the punishment of the offenders in Section 358 which states “Any person who commits the offence of rape is liable to imprisonment for life, with or without caning”.

The Criminal Code also provides for the unlawful carnal knowledge of under-aged girls, and people with unsound mind. The offence is tagged “defilement” in the Act and it provides thus:

“218. Any person who has unlawful carnal knowledge of a girl under the age of thirteen years is guilty of a felony; and is liable to imprisonment for life, with or without caning ...

220. It is a defence to a charge of any of the offences defined in the last preceding section to prove that the accused person believed, on reasonable grounds, that the girl was of, or above the age of sixteen years.”

²⁵ C.O. Okonkwo (n 1) 274.

²⁶ CAP C38 LFN 2004.

The punishment where the girl defiled is above thirteen years, but below sixteen years of age, or is an imbecile is however different. According to Section 22:

“Any person who:

(1) Has or attempts to have unlawful carnal knowledge of a girl being of, or above thirteen years, and under sixteen years of age; or

(2) Knowing a woman, or girl to be an idiot, or imbecile, has or attempts to have unlawful carnal knowledge of her; is guilty of a misdemeanor, and is liable to imprisonment for two years with or without caning”.

The provisions above show the initial state of the law of rape in Southern Nigeria as the Criminal Code was adopted and re-enacted as the Criminal Code Law of the southern states. It is obvious, that the definition of rape in this Act is limited in scope considering the different methods by which the crime is perpetrated in modern times. It still defines rape based on the sex of the victim, and the perpetrator; and it does not mention any way through which the victims of the crime can be helped.

The Criminal Code also reduces the punishment to two years, with or without caning where the victim is above thirteen years, but below sixteen years of age or is an imbecile.

3.1 PENAL CODE²⁷

The penal Code provides for the definition for the offence of rape in section 282 which has been stated earlier. The Penal Code further stipulates the punishment for the offence of rape in section 283 thus:

“Whoever has carnal intercourse against another of nature with any man, woman, or animal, shall be punished with imprisonment for a term which may extend to fourteen years. shall also be liable to fine.”

Furthermore, the penal Code clearly states that a girl below fourteen years of age, or of sound mind cannot be said to have given consent to the sexual intercourse, for age is capable to give such consent. Therefore, any unlawful carnal knowledge of such a girl, with or without her consent, amounts to rape.

²⁷ Penal Code (n 7).

3.2 ADMINISTRATION OF CRIMINAL JUSTICE ACT (ACJA), 2015

The Administration of Criminal Justice Act (ACJA) is a federal enactment on the administration of justice. It was enacted to unify the criminal procedures in all parts of Nigeria, thereby repealing the Criminal Procedure Act and Criminal Procedure Code initially regulating procedure in Southern and Northern respectively. While the Act does not define the offence of rape, it introduces innovative ideas in the procedure for the trial and administration of justice in rape cases.

Section 232 of the Act provides thus:

232(1) A trial for the offences referred to in subsection (4) of this section may not, where the court so determines, be held in an open court.

(2) The names, address, telephone numbers and identity of the victims such as offences or witness shall not be disclosed in any record or report of the proceedings, and it shall be sufficient to designate the names of the victims or witnesses with a combination of alphabets.

(3) Where in any proceeding the court deems it necessary to protect the identity of the victim or a witness, the court may take any or all the following measures:

(a) Receive evidence by video link;

(b) Permit the witness to be screened or masked;

(c) Receive written deposition of expert evidence; and

(d) Any other measure that the court considers appropriate in the circumstances.

(4) The provision of this section shall apply to:

(a) Offences under section 231 of this Act;

(5) Any contravention of the provisions of subsection (2) of this section shall be an offence and liable on conviction to a minimum term of one-year imprisonment.

The offences under section 231 are rape, defilement, and incest, unnatural or indecent offence against person. Therefore, the provision above seeks to protect the victim or witness where any of the offences is committed. The protection of victims and witnesses included in this part of ACJA is a welcome development, as it is capable of encouraging rape victims and key witnesses to report and give testimonies. It still remains under-reported because of the cultural beliefs and mind set of Nigerians, which usually leads to

exposure of the victims of rape to unnecessary ridicule and embarrassment by other members of the society.

The provision in Section 232 above clearly seeks to solve this problem by first stipulating that a rape trial may not be held in public where the court so desires. This provides an exception to the general rule that all trials must be held in an open court with public access. As a result of this provision, where the court observes that the nature of the rape trial may endanger the victim in one way or the other if it is held in an open court, the court may, pursuant to this section, order that the trial should not be held in public.

Furthermore, the section provides that the names, phone numbers and identity of victims of rape or witnesses shall not be disclosed even in the record of proceedings. It is enough, according to this provision, to designate their names with a combination of alphabets; the Act drives home this point by attaching a punishment to any form of derogation from this provision. This protects the victims and the witnesses in no small way as the fear of being stigmatized, blamed or looked down on has been dealt with. Furthermore, the Act in Section 232(3) provides that the court can receive evidence through other means other than physical oral testimony such as video link, written deposition, and having such witness or victim that needs to be protected screened or masked.

Moreover, the ACJA provides for the award of compensation to the victims of crimes. It empowers the courts, whether in a civil or criminal matter, to call for evidence while determining the commensurate compensation for the victim²⁸. Since the Penal Code and Criminal Code have no provision as to the compensation of victims, this is an encouraging and impressive development in the Nigerian Criminal Justice System. The Act applies to all criminal trials in Federal Courts including the Federal High Court, National Industrial Court, the Court of Appeal and the Supreme Court. The Act also applies to courts in the FCT, Abuja²⁹.

3.4 VIOLENCE AGAINST PERSONS (PROHIBITION) ACT 2015

The Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act (VAPPA) was passed into law in May 2015. The Act was passed as a result of agitations for protection of persons against the different

²⁸ Section 314, Administration of Criminal Justice Act.

²⁹ Ibid Section 2(1).

forms of domestic and public violence. It was the need to protect citizens from such violence that led to the enactment of VAPPA 2015. The Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act is an improvement on the penal and criminal code in relation to violence; it also makes provision for compensation to victims as well as the protection of their rights³⁰.

Section 1 of the Act provides thus:

- 1(1) A person commits the offence of rape if:*
 - (a) He or she intentionally penetrates the vagina, anus, or mouth of another person with any other part of his or her body or anything else;*
 - (b) The other person does not consent to the penetration or;*
 - (c) The consent is obtained by force or means of threat or intimidation of any kind or by fear of harm or by means of false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act or the use of any substance or additive capable of taking away the will of such person or in the case of a married person, by impersonating his or her spouse.*
- 2. A person convicted of an offence under subsection (1) of this section is liable to imprisonment for life except –*
 - (a) Where the offender is less than 14 years of age, the offender is liable to a maximum of 14 years imprisonment;*
 - (b) In all other cases, to a minimum of 12 years imprisonment without an option of fine, or*
 - (c) In the case of rape by a group of persons, the offenders are liable jointly to a minimum of 20 years imprisonment without an option of fine.*
- 3. The court shall also award appropriate compensation to the victim as it may deem fit in the circumstance.*
- 4. A register for convicted sexual offenders shall be maintained and accessible to the public.*

³⁰ <https://lawpavilion.com/blog/the-violence-against-person-prohibition-act-2015/accessed30th> April 2023.

By virtue of the above provisions, the Act expands the meaning of rape, embracing the other forms in which the offence is being committed in modern times. Thus, while other existing laws such as the Criminal and Penal Codes limit their scope of rape to protect only females in relation to vaginal penetration without consent, the Act has taken a giant stride to expand the meaning and scope of rape.

Under the Act, in addition to the vagina, rape is committed when any person, be it male or female, intentionally penetrates the anus or mouth of another person with any other part of his or her body or anything else without consent, or where such consent is obtained by force or means of threat or intimidation of any kind or by fear of harm or by means of threat or intimidation of any kind or by fear of harm or by means of false fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act or the use of false of any substance or additive capable of taking away the will of such person, or in the case of a married person by impersonating his or her spouse³¹.

It is worthy of note that, this expanded definition under the Act protects both males and females against rape, thereby settling the age-long issue of rape being gender biased as raised by jurists based on the traditional laws of rape in Nigeria.

Furthermore, by virtue of the definition of rape under this Act, it progressively took cognizance of the fact that sex now goes beyond the primary sex organs and thus, extended the scope of rape to include the anus and mouth. This is because it was difficult, in times past, to bring an issue of forceful anal or oral sex under the umbrella of rape simply because such occasion was not envisaged or accommodated by our laws. Furthermore, penetration under the Act now goes beyond penetration by the penis to include penetration by any other part of the body and even other objects.

Moreover, in punishing rape, the Act provides that the punishment for the offence of rape is life imprisonment. It however further provides for the punishment of offenders less than 14 years of age, which implies that the age of criminality set for 12 years under the Criminal Code has been reviewed under the Act and as such, a person below the age of 14 (not necessarily above 12 years old) can be guilty of rape under VAPP Act but the maximum

³¹ Section 1(a)-(c) Violence Against Person (Prohibition) Act 2015.

punishment in such cases is 14 years imprisonment. The Act also recognizes the possibility of having joint offenders, and thus provides for the appropriate punishment in such instances³².

Another important feature of the Act is its provision for compensation to victims of crimes under the Act. The Act provides that the Court shall award appropriate compensation to the victim as it may deem fit in the circumstances.³³ And in addition to the rights provided for under chapter IV of the Nigerian Constitution, victims, and survivors of violence are entitled to comprehensive medical, psychological, social and legal assistance by accredited service providers and government agencies or non-governmental agencies providing such assistance; information on the availability of legal, health and social services and other relevant assistance and be readily afforded access to them; rehabilitation and re-integration program³⁴.

The lawmakers, taking cognizance of the fact that victims or potential victims might not want to come forward to lodge complaints in relation to offences under the Act because of the fear of further victimization in the wider society (especially at the workplace), provide that no complainant of any offence under the Act shall be expelled, disengaged, suspended or punished in any form whatsoever by virtue of the action of compliance with the provisions of this Act.³⁵ The identities of victims of offences under the Act is also sought to be protected. The Act provides for the number and categories of persons that may be in court during a trial³⁶, it empowers the Court to hear proceedings in camera or to exclude any person from attending such proceedings³⁷ and prohibits the publication of certain information in relation to the trial.³⁸ This is to ensure that the dignity of the victim (and other parties to the trial) is protected.³⁹

According to the Act:

³² Ibid at Section 2 (a)- (c).

³³ Ibid., Section 3.

³⁴ Ibid., Section 38(1) (a)-(c).

³⁵ Ibid., Section 38(1) (e).

³⁶ Ibid., Section 38(3).

³⁷ Ibid., Section 38(4).

³⁸ Ibid., Section 39.

³⁹

(45) (1) Any offence committed or proceedings instituted before the commencement of this Act under the provisions of the –

(a) Criminal Code, Cap LFN 2004

(b) Penal Code, Cap LFN, 2004.

(c) Criminal Procedure Code Cap. LFN, 2004

(d) Any other law or regulation relating to any act of violence defined by this Act shall as the case may require, be enforced or continue to be enforced by the provisions of this Act.

(2) Any provision of the Act shall supersede any other provision in similar offences in the Criminal Code, Penal Code and Criminal Procedure Code.

Unfortunately, despite the progressive nature of VAPP Act and its all-encompassing provisions, the Act only applies only to the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.⁴⁰ However, some states in the federation have adopted the Act as law.

3.5 CRIMINAL LAW OF LAGOS STATE, 2011

The criminal Law of Lagos State, 2011, however, there is a provision for sexual assault by penetration. Section 259 of the law provides:

Any man who penetrates sexually the anus, vagina, mouth or any other opening in the body of another person with a part of his body or anything else, without the consent of the person is guilty of a felony and liable to imprisonment for life.

The definition of rape under the Criminal Law of Lagos state is more in line with what obtains at the international level. In the case of *Akayesu*,⁴¹ the tribunal defined rape as “a physical invasion of a sexual nature, committed on a person under circumstances which are coercive”. It defines acts of sexual violence to include, “forcible sexual penetration of the vagina, anus or oral cavity by penis and/or of the vagina or anus by some object, and sexual abuse such a forced nudity.”

In *Furundzija*⁴² the International Criminal Tribunal for Yugoslavia (ICTY) widened the definition of rape beyond what was defined in *Akayesu*.⁴³ The tribunal maintained that rape

⁴⁰ Section 47, Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015.

⁴¹ ICTR1998.

⁴² ICTY,1998.

⁴³ The trial of Jean-Paul Akayesu ICTR 1998.

comprises “the sexual penetration, however slight, either of the vagina or anus of the victim by the penis of the defendant, where such penetration is affected by coercion or force or threat of force against the victim or a third person.” thus, far beyond the local provisions which provides that sexual intercourse affected by force or threat of force to the victim amount to rape, under international law, sexual intercourse affected by the use of force or threat of force to, not just the victim but, also a third party, amount to rape.⁴⁴

The position is not particularly different under the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR).⁴⁵ The only difference is that unlike the ICTY Statute, the ICTR Statute does not require that the sexual act called in question must be connected to wartimes or armed conflict. Precisely, Art.3 (g) provides:

*The International Tribunal for Rwanda shall have the power to prosecute persons responsible for the following crimes when committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack against any civilian population on national, political ethnic, racial or religion grounds.*⁴⁶

To prove rape under domestic law, the slightest penetration is sufficient⁴⁷. According to Gledhill,⁴⁸ even the penetration of the vulva is sufficient to prove sexual intercourse.⁴⁹ There need not be omission of semen.⁵⁰ There need not be evidence of struggle.⁵¹ The *actus reus*, which is penetration, must be proved. Failure to prove penetration is fatal to the prosecution’s case.⁵²

4.0 IMPEDIMENTS TO THE PROSECUTION OF RAPE CASES IN NIGERIA

4.1 POOR REPORTAGE

Rape cases are grossly under-reported in Nigeria. Victims of rape cited some reasons for not reporting, including the stigma involved, lack of trust in the justice system, economic

⁴⁴ See Article 5. See also the case of prosecutor v Haradinaj Case IT-04-84 TICTY judgment of 3rd April 2008 para.122.

⁴⁵ The tribunal was established by Security Council Resolution NO.955 of 8th November 1994.

⁴⁶ Article 7: Crimes Against Humanity.

⁴⁷ Mu’azu v state(2022)12NWLR(pt1844)319sc.

⁴⁸ Gledhill A: The Penal Code of Northern Nigeria and the Sudan. London University Press London, 1975.436.

⁴⁹ Penal code Act and Sudan penal Code.

⁵⁰ Ogunbayo v state (2002)15 NWLR(pt789)100

⁵¹ Kammal v The state AIR. Here the accused had sexual intercourse with the prosecutrix in advanced stage of pregnancy. It was held that the fact the woman made no resistance does not imply consent.

⁵² Damuna v The State (2021)4 NWLR(pt1767)422CA.

factors, and rape myths and stereotypes, among other factors⁵³. The UN Human Rights Committee (HRC) has expressed concern over the low level of reporting of gender-based violence in Nigeria. The Committee highlighted factors such as “culture of silence perpetuated by persistent societal stereotypes; the lack of prompt and effective investigations of such cases; the low level of prosecution and conviction of perpetrators; and the insufficient level of assistance for victims.”

In cases of rape, a victim can decide to report the crime to the police, Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), National Agency for Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) or the SGBV Response Unit of the Federal Ministry of Justice. Victims, families of victims, or concerned individuals or organizations can also report rape. In some cases, victims report to Sexual Assault Referral Centers, civil society organizations, the National Human Rights Commission, or government ministries like the Ministry of Women Affairs and the Ministry of Justice, who then refer the case to the police for investigation, as well as prosecution. When the case is reported to the police station at the divisional level, an investigation police officer is assigned to investigate the case⁵⁴. The police officers are expected to take the victim to the hospital for medical examination and appropriate health care. The victim is entitled to decide whether forensic evidence may be collected or not to pursue legal redress. Subsequently, the statement of the victim or their parent/guardian (in the case where the victim is a child) is then recorded. The police then proceed to arrest the perpetrator and to visit the scene of the crime. At the scene of the crime, the police gather evidence that is crucial to the investigation. At the police station, the perpetrator’s statement would be taken under caution and the perpetrator might be detained. The case is then transferred from the division to the Criminal Investigation Department of the Nigeria Police Force, where the case is charged to court for prosecution⁵⁵.

⁵³ UN Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), General Recommendation 35: Gender-Based Violence against Women, 26 July 2017, UN Doc. CEDAW/C/GC/35, para. 21, p. 8.

⁵⁴ Interview in person with Lucia, rape survivor, 28 January 2020, Abuja.

⁵⁵ The Advocates for Human Rights, “Health Consequences of Sexual Assault”, stopvaw.org/health_consequences_of_sexual_assault (accessed on 7 February 2021)

4.2 ATTITUDES OF LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENTS TOWARDS VICTIMS

Police and other law enforcement agents are vital in ensuring justice for victims at all stages of the legal process from reporting to investigation and then during court trials. Vice President *Yemi Osinbajo* asserts that: “As first responders, they (police) play an important role in protecting victims not just from the commission of the crimes, but in ensuring that evidence that is collected at the scene of the crime is properly handled and processed⁵⁶. The entire experience of the victim depends largely on how law enforcement handles individual cases.”

Experiences shared by victims and NGOs working with them reveal that some conduct of police officers does not comply with international human rights law and standards. Such attitudes also contravene the provisions of the Nigeria Police Act, which stipulates that the Police Force is “charged with the responsibility for promoting and protecting the fundamental rights of all persons as guaranteed under the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act and other international legal instruments on human rights to which Nigeria is a signatory.”

At the point of reporting rape, victims often face a lack of gender sensitivity and empathy from the police. Bola, a victim, recalled that:

“Some policemen told me that I enjoyed it. In the morning, again another policeman came, and he kept saying, “You enjoyed it. How was it? It’s like you will get pregnant for this man.” He was using some unkind words on me. I even reported to their DPO (Divisional Police Officer). Then he said in case I sight him anywhere, I should let him know. That he would deal with the officer.”

Article 2 of the United Nations Code of Conduct for Law Enforcement Officials requires that in the performance of their duty, law enforcement officials shall respect and protect human dignity and maintain and uphold the human rights of all persons. As a human rights standard, police shall take rigorous official action to prevent the victimization of women

⁵⁶ World Health Organisation, “Sexual Violence”, [who.int/reproductivehealth/topics/violence/sexual_violence/en/](https://www.who.int/reproductivehealth/topics/violence/sexual_violence/en/) (accessed on 8 March 2021).

and shall ensure that re-victimization does not occur as a result of the omissions of police or gender-insensitive enforcement practices⁵⁷.

4.3 FINANCIAL COST OR CULTURAL INHIBITION

A crucial element in guaranteeing that justice systems are economically accessible to women is the provision of free or low-cost legal aid, advice, and representation in judicial and quasi-judicial processes in all fields of law. This is often not the reality for many victims in Nigeria. In Nigeria, there is a saying that “justice is sold to the highest bidder”. Victims of rape who are poor members of the society more often than not find themselves in a quagmire to prosecuting their cases⁵⁸. In some cases, while investigating rape, the police often transfer the financial burden to the victims. Most hospitals do not provide free forensic examination and medical care for victims. When a victim goes to the police station to report rape, most times, police officers ask the victims to pay for their transportation to the hospital and the cost of medical examination⁵⁹.

A victim will have to pay for the transportation of the police, pay for a file, pays for typing and all other logistics that the police need to investigate arrest and prosecute a case. According to the VAPP Act, police have a duty to provide transportation for victims to a safe place and the nearest hospital (where necessary), and to accompany the victim to their residence to collect personal belongings⁶⁰.

The opinion that, “justice is only for the highest bidder. If you cannot afford it, you don’t have money to be able to take care of justice processes, you cannot get justice.”

Such act of demanding money from victims by police officers amount to corruption. Hence, it is a breach of the Constitution and the Police Code of Conduct. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) under Schedule V on Code of Conduct for

⁵⁷Vesicovaginal Fistula (VVF) is a medical condition characterised by a hole “between the bladder and the vagina that allows the continuous involuntary discharge of urine.” Reichert M, Schwandner T, Hecker A, et al. *Surgical Approach for Repair of Rectovaginal Fistula by Modified Martius Flap*. *Geburtshilfe Frauenheilkd*. 2014;74(10):923–927. doi:10.1055/s-0034-1383149 www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4210382

⁵⁸ WHO, *Ensuring human rights within contraceptive programmes: A human rights analysis of existing quantitative indicators*, 2014 , p. 1.

⁵⁹ CEDAW, *Concluding Observations: Nigeria* (previously cited), para 37(b), p.12.

⁶⁰ Daily Post, “Bill on free, compulsory treatment for victims of sexual abuse passed into law in Akwa Ibom”, 24 September 2021, dailypost.ng/2021/09/24/bill-on-free-compulsory-treatment-for-victims-of-sexual-abuse-passed-into-law-in-akwa-ibom/.

Public Officers, provides that “a public officer shall not ask for or accept property or benefits of any kind for himself or any other person because of anything done or omitted to be done by him in the discharge of his duties.” The Constitution further provides that any allegation that a public officer has committed a breach of or has not complied with the provisions of the Code shall be made known to the Code of Conduct Bureau⁶¹.

Under Principle 6 of the Nigeria Police Code of Conduct, “police officers shall not compromise their integrity or that of the Force, by accepting, giving or soliciting any gratuity which could be reasonably interpreted as capable of influencing their official acts or judgments, or by using their status as a police officer for personal, commercial, or political gain.” It further provides that “effective mechanism shall be established to ensure the internal discipline and external control as well as the supervision of Police officers; and particular provisions shall be made, for the receipt and processing of complaints against police officers, made by members of the public and the result of the outcomes of such procedures will not be considered classified.

In addition to this is cultural inhibition, in the sense that many families feel reporting rape cases would tarnish the reputation of the family⁶². They rather keep it a secret to protect their image and reputation as well as that of the victim from being tarnished.

4.4 STIGMATIZATION AND VICTIM-BLAMING

Victims often emphasize that stigmatization and victim blaming are key factors that hinder the reporting of rape. Victims of rape shared distressing experiences of stigmatization and victim-blaming by law enforcement agents and private individuals⁶³.

Victims who summon the courage to report cases of rape are often subjected to stigmatization and victim-blaming by the police. Reports of rape are sometimes disbelieved by the police and other law enforcement agents. They launch an inquisition into the lifestyle and personality of the victim. The victims of rape often become overwhelmed with the approach to questioning. They are further traumatized by the police with questions

⁶¹ Federal Ministry of Justice, “Core Functions and Activities of the Ministry”, ustice.gov.ng/about-us/ (accessed on 18 August 2021).

⁶² Federal Ministry of Women Affairs, “Women and Gender Affairs: Brief on Women and Gender Affairs Department”, womenaffairs.gov.ng/index.php/articles/ncc (accessed on 18 August 2021).

⁶³ Federal Republic of Nigeria, “Women and Gender Affairs Department,” womenaffairs.gov.ng/index.php/articles/ncc (accessed on 14 September 2021).

like, 'You went to his house? What did you go there to do? Did he take you out? Did he buy you food? What were you doing outside at night?

Such acts by the police contravene Section 96 of the Police Act 2020, which stipulates that a police officer shall not, in discharging his duty, discriminate against a person in Nigeria, based on the person's gender, socio-economic status, etc. Furthermore, a police officer shall not "use a language, or act in such a way that suggests a bias towards a particular group." Principle three of the Nigeria Police Code of Conduct requires police officers to provide every person with professional, effective and efficient law enforcement services. Some victims do not report rape due to the social stigma that comes with it. They are often scared to speak up and to report, because of the way they would be perceived in the society. For some, protecting the family name is sacrosanct. In Nigeria, the family name seems to be tied to the vagina. Nobody wants the family name to be soiled, so, they don't want to talk about rape. That could also explain why they don't want to go to court, because they believe these are personal things that should not be said in an open court. Furthermore, the court case drags on for long, and of course, they have other daughters, and they don't want people referring to their family as that family where rape occurs. Sofia, 12 years old, who was raped by her neighbor, told Amnesty International that she stopped going to school, because of how people would look at her and talk about her. Another victim stated that: "At the police station, one of the policemen asked what took me to where I was raped. One of the police officers even said that after enjoying everything, I am here making a complaint... I don't want to go to court. Everybody will be talking about me. If it gets to my family, everybody will be talking about it. Any little thing I do, they will bring it up. Personally, I want him to go to jail, I want justice."

Stigma, victim-blaming and lack of prosecution and punishment of perpetrators fuel a culture of rape and impunity⁶⁴. He told Amnesty International that: "The rapist knows he is the one committing the offence, but at the end of the day, he will not be the one."

⁶⁴ UN Economic and Social Affairs, *Handbook for Legislation on Violence against Women*, 2010, p. 29.

4.5 NEGLIGENCE ON THE PART OF VICTIMS

Negligence on the part of the victim arises in situations where the victim is raped but refuses to take any step towards the prosecution of the case. Every so often, when report is made to the police or other relevant agencies, it could have been too late to arrest the perpetrator⁶⁵.

4.6 POOR SEX EDUCATION

In some cultures, discourse on the topic of sex is a taboo, particularly, between parents and their children, and as such the children are not equipped with requisite sex education. As a result, victims of rape may not deem it necessary to narrate to their parents or any other person that they have been raped⁶⁶. In some instances, the victims do not even see it as anything wrong and even if they are raped due to lack of or poor sex education, may choose to keep silent about it as though it is a norm.

4.7 SETTLEMENT OF RAPE CASES OUTSIDE THE CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM

Although rape is a crime in Nigeria, settlement of rape cases outside the criminal justice system is a common practice. When victims report rape, the police sometimes advise victims and perpetrators to settle the case outside the criminal justice system. In some of these instances, the police tell the perpetrator to plead with the victim or their families so that the case can be dropped and not prosecuted.

Alternatively, the police facilitate the process where the perpetrator pays some money to the victim so that the victim would abort their quest for justice. Sometimes, the perpetrator might bribe the police officers with some money, to end the case. Similarly, religious and community leaders instruct families of victims to settle outside the criminal justice system, to avoid the stigma associated with rape. With such settlements, perpetrators go unpunished, and a culture of impunity is fueled. Such settlements of rape cases lead to further violations of women's rights and impunity for rape because they are often hinged on patriarchal values, thereby having a negative impact on women's access to judicial review and remedies.

⁶⁵ National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons, "VAPP Act", naptip.gov.ng/vapp-act/ (accessed on 18 August 2021).

⁶⁶ Interview in person with Anthonia Ojenagbon, rape survivor and founder of "Tonia Bruised but not Broken", 19 December 2020, Lagos State.

Violence against women is a crime and must be treated as such, including when it occurs within the family. Article 4(2) of the Maputo Protocol provides that “State Parties shall take appropriate and effective measures to enact and enforce laws to prohibit all forms of violence against women, including unwanted or forced sex, whether the violence takes place in private or public.”

4.8 CONDITIONS IN POLICE STATIONS

Testimonies gathered from victims and NGOs reveal that police stations are sometimes not conducive for reporting, in terms of their physical set-up and infrastructure. It is required that police stations should be in such a condition that “privacy can be maintained, that the victim/survivor is safe and secure, that there will be no interruptions, ideally in a victim/survivor-friendly room or building, and where she will not come into contact with the alleged perpetrator.”

A police officer who was interviewed by Amnesty International expressed displeasure at the conditions of the station where he works. He told Amnesty International:

“According to the UN Standard we are supposed to have interview rooms and playgrounds for children, but it’s quite unfortunate we don’t have that. As you can see, this is what we have. Also, going by UNICEF standards, we don’t have the required space for victims to report what happened to them. Our office is small, as you can see. The victim and perpetrator most times face each other while we are taking their statements. Give the police the equipment they need to do the job. We use our personal money to investigate. We do charity work here because we have the passion for that.” – A police officer, Lagos State.

A police officer in charge of one of the police gender units emphasized that the condition of the section is not up to the required standard. She bemoaned the lack of an interview room, which deprives victims of privacy when reporting. She also complained that there is only one vehicle in the division, which makes it difficult to visit the crime scene, convey victims to the hospital and ensure the arrest of perpetrators. Likewise, she told Amnesty International that in some cases, police officers use their personal vehicles to visit crime scenes.

The need for confidentiality is not respected as you will see the victim right there telling her story, and you will see everybody walking in and saying, 'Oh is this girl who was raped? Is she the one?' So, for me, I feel that the protection is not enough at all. The identity of victims should be concealed. They should be in a very secure environment so that they can express themselves properly. Sometimes, the victims are put side by side with the perpetrator, and you know the perpetrator is looking at the victim... Then the victim can't even talk, can't even express herself, because she is afraid." Two police officers in the gender unit of a police division complained that they pay for office supplies and the transportation of s victims with their personal funds. One of them stated, "We buy things ourselves".

We bought chairs and everything. That is the issue with the gender office. It is supposed to be more equipped than this." The second police officer stressed, "We face a lot. Did you see this file here? We bought it from our own salary." They told Amnesty International that in some cases, they pay for the medical reports of victims, because the police gender units do not have specific funds assigned to the units to support victims. In most cases, forensic examination is not free for victims, in public and privately owned hospitals. Hence, indigent victims who cannot pay out of pocket are unable to access emergency medical care and forensic examination.

4.9 GAPS IN TRAINING OF LAW ENFORCEMENT OFFICERS

There are gaps in the training of law enforcement officers. The testimonies of people by revealed that law enforcement officers employ gender stereotypes, rape myths, victim blaming, stigmatization, lack of gender sensitivity and further violence.

The Inspector-General of Police is obligated to ensure that all police officers undergo periodic training and re-training on human rights, gender equality, public relations and other emerging issues. The Federal Government, in its 6th Periodic Report to the African Commission on Human and People's Rights, reported that a gender policy for the Nigeria Police Force was adopted in September 2012. It was also reported that there is a gender module in the Police National Human Rights Training Curriculum.

The UN Special Rapporteur on Violence Against Women has recommended that: "States must ensure the necessary training for members of the judiciary and legal and law enforcement professionals on international human rights standards and jurisprudence

regarding rape, and on the myths and stereotypes that still hinder the implementation of those standards.” Some police officers who work in the gender unit that were interviewed for this research emphasized that the training they got from the police college is insufficient.

5.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are the Recommendations:

1. Death penalty; a person found guilty of the offence of rape should be sentenced to death either by hanging, fringing squad, lethal injection, electrocution etc.
2. Closed trial; in Nigeria, rape cases are in the open court. With the fear that, or people will be staring at the victim and also the shame, a victim may not be willing to report the matter to the police or other established body.
3. Definition of the offence; there is a need for the review of the law on rape in Nigeria to expand the definition and make it an offence for both sexes.
4. Definition of consent; it is recommended that consent should be expressly defined in the Criminal Code and other relevant Statutes.
5. Adoption of the Violence Against Persons (Prohibitions) Act, 2015; the lawmakers of both the federal and states level should work towards ensuring that the VAPP Act is adopted by all states of the federation to regulate domestic violence and all forms of sexual abuses as reports show that only fifteen (15) states have so far signed into law.
6. Parents should focus on using the same effort and energy raising the female child to raise the male child becoming a responsible adult in the society. Children should be taught everything they need to know about consent from an early age. The family is a fundamental unit in the society, and it will be heard to instill certain values that haven't been taught at home.

6.0 CONCLUSION

Considering the different advancements of the modern world, the law should be amended, and the definition should be expanded to enable the agencies assigned to curb this menace as it is increasing daily and the government should see reasons why there is need for amendment rather than reading recommendations as a fruitless exercise.

Furthermore, victims of rape should be offered some protection, encouragement to voice out and confidentiality within the scheme of criminal justice architecture which allows which allows essential persons to be present in court. Proactive sensitization programs on stigmatization should be organized for both the male and female gender on the act of rape and the government should support non-governmental organizations as they play a vital in assisting the victims in the country even when they cannot do the police.